

Definition of an Algebraic Graph With Applications

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Abstract

This paper is on a structure that can be thought of as a set of simple graphs. An algebraic graph is defined as a set of graphs with an induced subgraph concept within the structure. A concept of stability is defined for the graph in terms of an algebraic lower graph. The resulting formula can be applied in architectural engineering and social sciences. The stability of several graphs was evaluated.

1 Introduction

In this article, the algebraic graph is introduced that can be expressed as a simple equation, and several theorems can be applied from graph coloring theory. A formula is proposed regarding the stability of general graphs utilized in various fields of industry.

2 Main text

2.1 Definition of Algebraic Graph

In the following are several definitions for an algebraic graph.

Definition 1. *Rearranged Set.* $R(G) := \{X : V(G) = V(X), G \cong X\}$

This definition is intuitive to understand. It is a set of graphs which is isomorphic with G . It is expressing isomorphism of graph more easily. But it has a difference with respect to the concept of Rearranged Set having vertexes of the elements of $R(G)$ always equal with G . But the graph isomorphism doesn't have to be different.

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Definition 2. $G_1 \subseteq G_2 \Leftrightarrow V(G_1) \subseteq V(G_2), E(G_1) \subseteq E(G_2)$

Definition 3. $G_1 \subseteq_E G_2 \Leftrightarrow V(G_1) = V(G_2), E(G_1) \subseteq E(G_2)$

Definition 2 and 3 are about inclusion relationship of graph.

Definition 4. $A \subseteq_V B \Leftrightarrow \exists_{S \subseteq V(B)} : A = B[S]$

The induced subgraph is denoted as the following expression.

Definition 5. *Rearranged Induced Subgraph.* $G_1 \subseteq_{RV} G_2 \Leftrightarrow \exists_{a \in R(G_1), b \in R(G_2)} : a \subseteq_V b$

The difference between definition 4 and 5 is that definition 5 includes the concept of definition 4 and a rearranged set, simultaneously.

Definition 6. $G_1 \subseteq_{RE} G_2 \Leftrightarrow \exists_{a \in R(G_1), b \in R(G_2)} : a \subseteq_E b$

Definition 7. $G_1 \subseteq_R G_2 \Leftrightarrow \exists_{G_0 \in R(G_1)} : G_0 \subseteq G_2$

Definition 5, 6 and 7 introduce the inclusion relationship of graphs with a rearranging set. This is a common inclusion relationship.

Definition 8. $W(A, R) := \begin{cases} 1, & \exists_{a, b \in A} : aRb \\ 0, & \forall_{a, b \in A} : \sim aRb \end{cases}$

This definition may be less intuitive to understand. The main text will clarify the idea.

This definition is a characteristic function that determines which binary relationship R , defined over the set A , is related to at least two elements of the set. The function has a value of zero if the relationship does not give any relation over the set, and a value of one if any one pair of elements can be related by that relation R .

An algebraic graph is defined in terms of the following.

Definition 9. *Let AG be a set of algebraic graphs, $G \in AG \Leftrightarrow g \not\subseteq_{RV} G$*

G being in an algebraic graph is equivalent with that G doesn't have g as an induced subgraph. g is the following graph, figure 1.

Figure 1: A contradicting graph, g

The reason for defining it as an algebraic graph is that it is the only one graph set which can be expressed as an equation. Then it is introduced how to express a graph as an equation. Let us consider vertexes in a graph as solutions of an

equation. If an edge exists between 2 vertexes, the solutions which the vertexes refer to are different from each other, else they are equal. Then the minimum-degree equation which includes all solutions in a graph is that equation which refers to the graph, the only one.

There exists a property in non-algebraic graphs, that they always need more edges to colorize as connected vertexes are different, non-connected vertexes are same. This is an important property to prove the theorem.

Definition 10. *If $G \in AG$ and its algebraic expression is $f(x) = 0$, then $G \sim f(x)$*

This definition makes the algebraic expression of a graph more simple.

2.1.1 Expanded Definition of a Complete Graph with an Algebraic Expression of a Graph

Every complete graph is an algebraic graph. The reason is that all vertexes in a complete graph are connected because of the definition of a complete graph, so they can be expressed as $(x - \alpha_1)(x - \alpha_2) \cdots (x - \alpha_n)$. Using this feature, the definition of a complete graph is expanded with the algebraic expression of a graph.

Definition 11. $G \in K_{ex} \Leftrightarrow G \sim (x - \alpha_1)^m(x - \alpha_2)^m \cdots (x - \alpha_n)^m$

In this case, this graph is called as an n -degree m -character complete graph.

2.1.2 The Chromatic Number of an Algebraic Graph

The chromatic number of an algebraic graph is trivially equal with the number of distinct solutions of the equation which expresses the graph. It can be written mathematically as the following term, and it's trivial because of the definition of the algebraic graph.

Theorem 1. $G \sim f(x) \Rightarrow \chi(G) = (\text{Number of distinct solutions of } f(x) = 0)$

2.1.3 Property of the Chromatic Number of a Graph

In general, the following proposition can be utilized.

$$G_1 \subseteq_R G_2 \Rightarrow \chi(G_1) \leq \chi(G_2)$$

The contrapositive proposition is used here. That is indicated in the following theorem. The proof of this theorem is left out because it's trivial.

Theorem 2. $\chi(A) < \chi(B) \Rightarrow [A \subsetneq_R B \text{ or } W(\{A, B\}, \subseteq_R) = 0]$

2.1.4 Number of an Algebraic Graph and Its Integer Partitions

The number of algebraic graphs whose vertex number is n , is surprisingly equal to the partition number n .

Theorem 3. $AG_n := \{G \in AG : V(G) = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}\}$
 \Rightarrow (number of distinct elements of AG_n) = p_n

Proof. Let $G \in AG$ and the vertex number to be n and let $G \sim f(x)$. And let $\{\alpha_n\}$ to be a set of distinct solutions of $f(x) = 0$, let a_i to be a number of same solution with α_i . Then the problem changes to find $|\{\{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_n\} : a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + \dots + a_n = n \text{ and } a_i \in \mathbb{N}_0\}|$. This is equal to p_n . \square

2.2 Algebraic Lower and Upper Graphs

The algebraic lower graph and algebraic upper graphs are defined in the following. Briefly, the algebraic upper graph is the set of algebraic graphs which is supremum with relation \subseteq_E than original graph. The algebraic lower graph is its contrary.

The algebraic lower and upper graphs are defined as below.

Definition 12. $\max_G S := \{G \in S : \forall K \in S : [K \subseteq_E G \text{ or } W(\{G, K\}, \subseteq_E) = 0]\}$

Definition 13. $\min_G S := \{G \in S : \forall K \in S : [G \subseteq_E K \text{ or } W(\{G, K\}, \subseteq_E) = 0]\}$

Definition 14. $f_l(G) := \max_G \{X : X \subseteq_E G, X \in AG\}$

Definition 15. $f_u(G) := \min_G \{X : G \subseteq_E X \in AG\}$

What should not be confused is that the $\max_G S$ and $\min_G S$ are not just a graph. These are sorts of graph sets. The 'G' under 'max' or 'min' is just suffix. The symbol of this expression had fixed suffix 'G'. Trivially, the algebraic upper and lower graphs exist on any graph, because of the existence of a complete graph and an edgeless graph.

2.2.1 Chromatic Number of an Algebraic Upper Graph

In 2.2.1 is proven a theorem that shows the perspective which the chromatic number of a graph is equal to the chromatic number of an algebraic upper graph. This is the first application of the concept of an algebraic upper graph.

The $f_u(G)$ usually doesn't have only one graph. But their chromatic numbers are the same. It is introduced in theorem 6. Following lemma 4 and 5 are important while proving theorem 6.

Lemma 4. $\forall A, B \in AG_n : \chi(A) < \chi(B) \Rightarrow W(\{A, B\}, \subseteq_E) = 1$

This is trivial by the definition of an algebraic graph.

Lemma 5. $\forall A, B \in f_u(G) : W(\{A, B\}, \subseteq_E) = 0$

This is also trivial by the definition of an algebraic upper graph.

Theorem 6. $\forall_{A,B \in f_u(G)} : \chi(A) = \chi(B)$

Proof. If $\chi(A) \neq \chi(B) \Rightarrow W(\{A,B\}, \subseteq_E) = 1$ by lemma 4. But by lemma 5, $\forall_{A,B \in f_u(G)} : W(\{A,B\}, \subseteq_E) = 0$. But it is a contradiction. So theorem 6 can be proven by these inferences. \square

This theorem was expanded to theorem 7. It explains the chromatic number of a general graph.

Theorem 7. $\forall_{A \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(A)$

Proof. This is obvious when $G \in AG$. By theorem 6, to prove this proposition, $\forall_{A \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(A)$ is equivalent with $\exists_{A \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(A)$. Therefore, the proposition $G \notin AG \Rightarrow \exists_{K:G \subseteq_E K} : \chi(G) = \chi(K)$ is correct. Because a non-algebraic graph always needs more edges to color connected vertexes different, non-connected vertexes are the same. Trivially, it can be substituted with $G \notin AG \Rightarrow \exists_{K:G \subseteq_E K \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(K)$. It proves theorem 7. \square

The following terms are lemmas to prove theorem 10.

Lemma 8. $\exists_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a \Rightarrow \chi(a) \geq n$

Lemma 9. $G_0 \in AG : \chi(G_0) \geq n \Rightarrow K_n \subseteq_V G_0$

Lemmas 8 and 9 are trivial because of the definition of an algebraic graph so the proof is ignored.

Theorem 10. $\exists_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a \Leftrightarrow \forall_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a$

Proof. $\chi(a) \geq n$ because $\exists_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a$. And by theorem 7, $\chi(a) = \chi(G)$ so that $\forall_{a \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(a) \geq n$. So applying lemma 9, $\forall_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a$. It proves theorem 10. \square

2.3 Definition of the Stability of a Graph

In 2.3, is introduced the first application of the algebraic lower graph with a concept of stability of the graph. The formula about the stability of a graph can be applied in architectural engineering, social sciences and various parts of graph theory.

2.3.1 Background for Researching

Truss and arch are representative stable architectural structures being utilized in many kinds of buildings. Almost stable or unstable structures applied in architecture can be expressed as graphs.

The motivation for this paper was to show the stability of these architectural graphs. And finally important method was obtained for the numerical value of stability.

Various indicators can be applied when calculating the stability of a graph. One could use the summation of the degree of vertexes to calculate it, being simple. It

may be possible to construct algorithms by applying different complex invariants and theory, but algorithms were constructed with a chromatic number, instead.

In 2.3.2 is introduced the basic idea for the definition of the stability of a graph. Main definitions of stability are introduced of the graph in 2.3.3. And in 2.3.4, some examples for these concepts are shown.

2.3.2 The Basic Idea for an Algorithm

The fundamental method to evaluate the stability of a graph is to count how many vertexes are connected with other vertexes. Then the stability can be evaluated by the degree of vertexes or by the a chromatic number of a graph. This was also discussed in section 2.3.1.

Let the graph G to be evaluated in stability. One can think of the situation that G loses some edges and forms an algebraic graph (one can certainly calculate the stability of this graph in a convincing way). In other words, the graph forms algebraic lower graph. The new graph is more unstable than the original graph (it is analogous to a building being slightly damaged by an impact, whatever its deformation, it makes a decrease in the stability).

This would indicate a slightly more corrected stability from the original stability. That is, how stable the graph is over its algebraic lower graph may be another indicator of its stability. If stability is calculated by the chromatic number of a graph, the various definitions which will appear next can be defined more simply. Thus one defined the stability by the chromatic number of a graph.

2.3.3 Definition of the Stability of a Graph

In 2.3.2, was introduced the fundamental idea to define the stability of a graph. The main definition that defines the stability of the graph and an important property in 2.3.3. was introduced.

The following definition is written based on the discussion in the 2.3.2.

Definition 16. *If $G \notin AG$, $A \in f_l(G)$ the stability can be defined as $s := \chi(G) - \chi(A)$*

This is a definition of the stability of a graph when the graph is not an algebraic graph. But this definition can't be applied when the graph is an algebraic graph. Because the algebraic lower graph of an algebraic graph is always itself. So a new definition is required for this problem.

Definition 17. *If $G \in AG$,*

$$T := \{a : e \in E(G), K = G - \{e\}, A \in f_l(K), a = \chi(K) - \chi(A)\}$$

the stability can be defined as

$$s := \frac{\min T + \max T}{2}$$

Let's take a closer look at what the above definition means. K is a graph which loses an edge from G and A is an algebraic lower graph of K . T is a set that has a as an element and a is the difference between $\chi(K)$ and $\chi(A)$. So T is a set of differences between G and the algebraic graph of G . But as the algebraic lower graph of an algebraic graph is itself, we made it by force with the very K .

We can understand definition 17 with these inferences.

Using this definition, the problem observed with G as an algebraic graph, can be solved.

Now, the expanded forms of these definitions are introduced. Definition 20 explains the general definition of stability of the graph.

Definition 18. $I_{m_1}(G) = I_{M_1}(G) := f_1(G)$ and inductively,

$$I_{m_k}(G) := \min_G \{G_0 : a \in I_{m_{k-1}}(G), e \in E(a), G_0 \in f_1(a - \{e\})\}$$

$$I_{M_k}(G) := \max_G \{G_0 : a \in I_{M_{k-1}}(G), e \in E(a), G_0 \in f_1(a - \{e\})\}$$

This definition is important to explain the algebraic lower graph of an algebraic graph.

Definition 19. $n_{min} := \min\{i : I_{m_i}(G) = \{\text{(edgeless graph)}\}\}$, $n_{max} := \min\{i :$

$$I_{M_i}(G) = \{\text{(edgeless graph)}\}\}, \alpha(G) := \begin{cases} 1, & G \in AG \\ 0, & G \notin AG \end{cases}$$

Then we can define the stability as

$$s(G) := \frac{n_{min} + n_{max}}{2} + \alpha(G)$$

The $\alpha(G)$ is characteristic function of algebraic graph.

Finally, the general formula of the stability of the graph, $s(G)$ is defined.

The reason the definition of the stability of a general graph is stated without chromatic number is, if so that, the stability can't include more deep structure. To solve this problem, the stability is defined with n_{min} and n_{max} .

Generally and trivially, the stability is maximum when the graph is a complete graph and minimum when the graph is an edgeless graph.

2.3.4 Application to Various Graphs

In this subsection, one evaluated the stability of the various famous graphs.

Figure 2: $K_{2,2}$

$s(K_{2,2})$ (Figure 2) is 2 by formula definition 19.

Figure 3: $K_{3,3}$

$s(K_{3,3})$ (Figure 3) is 2 by formula definition 19.

Figure 4: Cube graph

$s(\text{Cube graph})$ (Figure 4) is 1 by formula definition 19.

Figure 5: K_4

$s(K_4)$ (Figure 5) is 4 by formula definition 19.

These results are showing that the important factor of stability of a graph is not number of edges, but the arrangement of edges.

To the readers who have come this far, appreciation is given.

3 Discussion

Theorem 7 can change how we think about the chromatic numbers of graphs. In the past, researchers considered that the chromatic number is a property of a graph which cannot find a relation with edges. There was no theorem and definition to calculate the chromatic number of a graph related to an edge [2]. But it turned out to be wrong as shown in the preceding sections.

The concept of an algebraic graph can be applied in the abstract algebra and elicit the concept of stability of a graph. It has a lot of use in form and suits a definition, but that definition has some troubles, too. In some cases, a pair of perfectly different graphs can be similar in value and this happens

frequently. We must solve this as the next problem. But the reason that these are significant is that the more vertexes the more correct a stability value can be obtained with these definitions.

4 Conclusion

In this article theorems 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 10 were proven and the stability of the graph was defined. All of these results imply the necessity and importance of an algebraic graph in the mathematical section of graph theory. The main theorems are summarized as follows.

Theorem. $G \sim f(x) \Rightarrow \chi(G) = (\text{Number of distinct solutions of } f(x) = 0)$

Theorem. $\chi(A) < \chi(B) \Rightarrow [A \subsetneq_R B \text{ or } W(\{A, B\}, \subseteq_R) = 0]$

Theorem. $AG_n := \{G \in AG : V(G) = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}\}$
 $\Rightarrow (\text{number of distinct elements of } AG_n) = p_n$

Theorem. $\forall_{A, B \in f_u(G)} : \chi(A) = \chi(B)$

Theorem. $\forall_{A \in f_u(G)} : \chi(G) = \chi(A)$

Theorem. $\exists_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a \Leftrightarrow \forall_{a \in f_u(G)} : K_n \subseteq_V a$

Definition. $I_{m_1}(G) = I_{M_1}(G) := f_l(G)$ and inductively,

$$I_{m_k}(G) := \min_G \{G_0 : a \in I_{m_{k-1}}(G), e \in E(a), G_0 \in f_l(a - \{e\})\}$$

$$I_{M_k}(G) := \max_G \{G_0 : a \in I_{M_{k-1}}(G), e \in E(a), G_0 \in f_l(a - \{e\})\}$$

Definition. $n_{min} := \min\{i : I_{m_i}(G) = \{\text{edgeless graph}\}\}, n_{max} := \min\{i :$

$$I_{M_i}(G) = \{\text{edgeless graph}\}\}, \alpha(G) := \begin{cases} 1, & G \in AG \\ 0, & G \notin AG \end{cases}$$

Then we can define the stability as

$$s(G) := \frac{n_{min} + n_{max}}{2} + \alpha(G)$$

The $\alpha(G)$ is characteristic function of algebraic graph.

5 Reference

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